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Review Article

**ULAT KAMBAL (ABROMA AUGUSTA L.): THERAPEUTIC
USES AND PHARMACOLOGICAL STUDIES-A REVIEW**Ansar Ahmad^{*1}, Mohd Afsahul Kalam², Afreen Habeeb³ and Mohammad Asif Khan⁴¹*Professor Department of Ilmul Advia, Regional Research Institute of Unani Medicine,
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Jaipur. 302002**Article Received:** September 2020 **Accepted:** September 2020 **Published:** October 2020**Abstract:**

The plant Ulat Kambal (Abroma augusta L.) or Devil's cotton is belongs to the family Malvaceae. It is a lesser known drug of the Tibb-i-Unani. Almost all parts of the plant are used for the treatment of various ailments. It reported that the plant has a broad range of therapeutic potential. Fresh juice from root bark is useful in congestive and neuralgic forms of dysmenorrhea, amenorrhea, urinary trouble, bronchitis, bronchopneumonia, carbuncles and poisonous boils. Leaves used in diabetes, rheumatic pain and sinusitis. The plant contains taraxerol, its acetate and lupeol therefore useful in treating uterine disorders. General overview along with therapeutic uses of medicinal plant Abroma augusta L. are explained in this review.

Keywords: Ulat Kambal, Abroma augusta L. Gynecological disorders, Tibb-i-Unani

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INTRODUCTION:

Medicinal plants play a vital role in the treatment of various diseases from the time immemorial. In the recent years, plant derived products gain much more importance in the world in the form of medicinal products, nutraceuticals and cosmetics. Herbal formulations have reached widespread acceptability as therapeutic agents for the treatment of various disorders. Plants offer important source of food and drugs for human being since very early age and many of the available drugs have been derived from plant and other natural sources.¹ One such drug is Ulat Kambal (*Abroma augusta* L.), it is an evergreen small shrub with a long history of medicinal uses and mostly found in tropical Asia, South Eastern Africa and Australia. Indigenous or cultivated throughout the hotter parts of India, Java, Philippines, China. India from Punjab and Uttar Pradesh to Arunachal Pradesh, Assam, Meghalaya and Tripura.^{2,3,4} Almost all the parts of the plant are used in the treatment of diseases. Leaves and seeds of *Abroma augusta* L. are considered to be edible in India and New Genia.⁵ Almost all the parts of the plant are used in the treatment of diseases. The root wood and root bark are reputed remedies as an emmenagogue and uterine tonic, used in amenorrhea for congestive and nervous dysmenorrhea, irregular menses. The leaves are reported to be useful in treating uterine disorders, diabetes, rheumatic pains of joints, and headache with sinusitis. The cold aqueous infusion of the fresh leaves and twigs have been reported to be demulcent and very efficacious in gonorrhoea.⁶ The whole plant contains alkaloids, flavonoids, triterpenes, megastigmanes, steroids and phenylthanoic glycosides. Abromine, the active constituent of the *A. augusta* identified as betaine is responsible for antihyperglycemic activity. The leaves contain octacosanol, taraxerol, β -sitosterol acetate, Lupeol, an aliphatic alcohol (C32H66O) and mixture of long chain fatty diols.^{5,7}

Distribution:

Indigenous or cultivated throughout the hotter parts of India, Java, Philippines, China. In India it is found in Punjab, Uttar Pradesh, Arunachal Pradesh, Tripura, Meghalaya, Assam.^{3,4}

Botanical Description:

A shrub or small tree with velvety branches. Leaves 4-6 by 4-5 in. repand-denticulate, base 3-7 nerved, upper smaller, narrower, entire, glabrescent above, tomentose below; petiole 1/2-1 in.; Stipules linear, deciduous as long as the petiole. Peduncle 1 1/2 in., axillary; Flowers 2 in. diameter, dark red. Sepals 1 in., lanceolate, free nearly to the base. Petals scarcely exceeding the sepals, imbricate in the bud, deciduous;

Capsule 1 1/2 in. obpyramidal ultimately glabrous, thrice as long as the persistent calyx.^{4,8}

Scientific Classification:

Kingdom: Plantae
Division: Tracheophyta
Class: Magnoleopsida
Order: Malvales
Family: Malvaceae
Genus: Abroma
Species: augusta

Description in Unani Literature:

It is a shrub; its leaves are broad and have trichomes on the lower surface. Its branches have also trichomes and this make them soft and velvety. The color of the flower is dark red. The flowers resemble the nails of lion and they are anteverted and for this reason the name Ulat Kambal is given to this plant. Its fruit has 5 sections which breaks when it ripens and from all the 5 sections a silky cotton comes out. The seeds are multiple and black and resemble the seeds of radish. The color of seeds is black, bark is whitish in color.^{9,10}

Vernacular Name:

Ayurveda: Pishaacha Kaarpaasa, Pivari
Bengali: Olatkambol
English: Devil's Cotton, Perennial Indian Hemp
Gujarati: Ulak tambool
Hindi: Kumal, Ulatkambal, Sanukapashi
Sanskrit: Pivari, Pishaacha Kaarpaasa
Siddha/Tamil: Sivapputtuti
Unani: Ulat Kambal

Af'al (Pharmacological Action):

Mudirr-i-Hayd (emmenagogue), *Mukhrrij-i-Janin* (abortifacient), *Mudirr-i-Laban* (galactotrophic), *Muhallil* (anti-inflammatory), *Muqawwi-i-Mi'da* (stomachic), *Quruh-i-majra-i-bawl* (urethral ulcer).^{3,4,9,10,11}

Iste'malat (Therapeutic Uses):

- It is an emmenagogue and is used in females in infertility, irregular menses, oligomenorrhoea.^{3,4,9,10}
- Fresh juice from root bark useful in congestive and neuralgic forms of dysmenorrhoea, amenorrhoea, urinary trouble, bronchitis, bronchopneumonia, carbuncles and poisonous boils.⁴
- Leaves can be used in diabetes, rheumatic pain and sinusitis.^{4,11}
- Its tincture has been found effective in diabetes mellitus.¹⁰

- It's 6 g root powder with black peppers acts as stomachic. This powder is also useful in piles.¹⁰
- The root bark is used for sores. A paste of the root is used internally and externally to cure abscess.⁴
- It has also shown a tonic contractile action on the uterus therefore; the drug must be taken prior to starting of menses by two days.^{4,9,10}
- In Bengal region the nurses have been using this drug for oligomenorrhoea and infertility since long time.^{4,10}
- In the Indian Materia Medica, it is mentioned the infusion prepared from fresh leaves and branches of this tree in cold water, is very useful in urethritis.¹⁰
- The active principle of this drug is totally destroyed if mixed with alcohol of any other preservative; either the fresh root bark or dried root bark should be used.⁴

Doses: Dry bark: 2-4 gm; fresh bark: 4-8 gm; juice of fresh root: 3gm; siyal rub: 1-2 dram.⁹

Scientific studies

Phytochemistry:

The root bark of the plant contains mixed oils, resins, alkaloids and water-soluble bases. The root contains abromine, friedlin, abromasterol A, choline, beta-sitosterol, sigmasterol and octacosanol. The leaves of *Abroma augusta* L. contain taraxerol, its acetate and lupeol.^{3,4}

Pharmacological Studies:

Antibacterial activity: The plant shows significant antibacterial activities against three gram positive (*Bacillus subtilis*, *Bacillus megaterium*, *Staphylococcus aureus*) and four gram – negative (*Escherichia coli*, *Shigella dysenteriae*, *Shigella sonnei* and *Salmonella typhi*) bacteria.¹²

Antifungal activity: The antifungal activity of *Abroma augusta* L. was found strong against five fungi (*Aspergillus flavus*, *Aspergillus niger*, *Candida albicans*, *Rhizopus oryzae* and *Aspergillus fumigatus*).¹²

Antidiabetic activity: A clinical study shows significant reduction in blood glucose levels in cases of type 2 diabetes mellitus with *Abroma Augusta* Mother Tincture. *Abroma augusta* L. plays an important role in the treatment of Type 2 diabetes mellitus. There was no side effective during the treatment.¹³

Antioxidant activity: A study was carried out to screen the antioxidant property by measuring total phenolic, total flavonoid, total antioxidant activity, ferric reducing power capacity and DPPH radical scavenging activity test of four different fractions of *A. augusta* L. leaves extract. It shows significant antioxidant activity that might be due to their diverse phenolic constituents in the isolated extractives.¹⁴

Growth Inhibitory Activity against EAC cells: The bark extract of *A. augusta* L. shows anti-proliferative activity and this was observed using hemocytometer by counting EAC cells using trypan blue dye.²

Wound healing activity: The alcoholic extract of *Abroma augusta* L. was found to reverse dexamethasone suppressed wound healing.¹⁵

Hypolipidemic activity: Aqueous extract of curcumin obtained from *C. longa* and partially purified product from Devil's cotton showed marked decrease in lipid level in streptozotocin induced diabetic rats.¹⁶

Thrombolytic activity: Plant showed significant thrombolytic activity which was determined by using in vitro clot lysis assay method.¹⁷

Analgesic activity: The hexane extract of *Abroma augusta* L. showed the antinociceptive responses in acetic acid induced writhings, formalin, hot plate and tail flick tests. The extract exhibited the analgesic activity via peripheral and central mechanism both at supraspinal levels.¹⁸

Antipyretic activity: The hexane extract of *Abroma augusta* L. suppressed fever induced by yeast in rats. The antipyretic mechanism is probably due to inhibition of prostaglandin E₂ synthesis within the hypothalamus.¹⁸

Anti-inflammatory activity: The hexane extract of *Abroma augusta* L. exhibited the anti-inflammatory activity in acute phase by inhibition of the rat paw edema, the possible mechanism of the observed anti-inflammatory activity might be related to its ability to inhibit the release of bradykinin or prostaglandins synthesis, but the extract did not have anti-inflammatory activity in chronic inflammation using cotton pellet induced granuloma formation in rats.⁸¹

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REFERENCES:

1. Patel DK and Dhanabal SP. Determination of bioanalytical parameters for the standardization of *Abroma augusta*. Journal of Acute Disease. 2013; pp.292-295.
2. Miah M, Shimu AJ, Mahmud S, Omar FJ, Khatun R, Mohanto SC et al. Methanolic Bark extract of *Abroma augusta* (L.) induces apoptosis in EAC cells through altered expression of apoptosis regulatory genes. Evidence-based complementary and alternative medicine. 2020; pp. 1-14.
3. Khare CP. Indian Medicinal Plants: An Illustrated Dictionary. Springer Pvt. Ltd. New Delhi. 2007; pp. 2,3.
4. Kirtikar KR and Basu BD. Indian Medicinal Plants. 2nd ed. Vol. III. Delhi: Periodical Expert Book Agency; 2012: 380,381.
5. Khanra R, Dewanjee S, Dua TK, Sahu R, Gangopadhyay M, Feo VD et al. *Abroma augusta* L. (Malvaceae) leaf extract attenuates diabetes induced nephropathy and cardiomyopathy via inhibition of oxidative stress and inflammatory response. Journal of Translational Medicine. 2015; 13(6): pp. 1-14.
6. Mondal OA, Haque E, Haque E, Khan AR. Repellent activity of *Abroma augusta* extracts against *tribolium castaneum* (herbst) adults. J.bio-sci. 2012; 20: pp.49-55.
7. Mir SJ, Darzi MM, Mir MS. Efficacy of *Abroma augusta* on Biochemical and Histomorphological Features of Alloxan-Induced Diabetic Rabbits. Iranian Journal of Pathology. 2013; 8 (3): pp. 153 – 158.
8. Hooker JD. The Flora of British India. Part I, International Book Distributer, Dehradun. 1872; pp.375.
9. Kabiruddin M. Magzanul Mufradat. Idara Kitab Us Shifa, New Delhi; 2014: pp. 54,55.
10. Multani H. Hindustan aur Pakistan ki jadi butiyan aur unke fawaid. Gazni street, Lahore; pp. 23,25.
11. Pullaiah T. Encyclopaedia of World Medicinal Plants, Vol. I. Regency Publications, New Delhi. p. 15.
12. Saikot FK, Khan A, Hasan MF. Antimicrobial and cytotoxic activities of *Abroma augusta* Linn. leaves extract. Asian Pacific Journal of Tropical Biomedicine. 2012; 2(3): pp. S1418-S1422.
13. Reddy ESR, Sharma PK, Raj P. Effect of *Abroma augusta* mother tincture in type 2 diabetes mellitus by assessing blood glucose levels- a clinical study. 2018; 9(3): pp. 24687-24691.
14. Mannan MA, Hossen MZ, Islam Z, Haque ABHM, Zahan MK, Zaman S. Bangladesh Journal of Industrial Microbiology and Biotechnology. Assessment of Antioxidant Properties of the Medicinal Plant *Abroma augusta* Linn. (Sterculiaceae) Leave. 2017; 1(2).
15. Shanbag T, Dattachauduri A, Shenoy S, Bairy KL. Wound healing activity of *Abroma augusta* in Wistar rats. Asian Pac J Trop Med. 2009; 2(4): 6-10.
16. Eshrat MH. Hypoglycemic, Hypolipidemic and antioxidant properties of combination of curcumin from *Curcuma longa* Linn. and partially purified product from *Abroma augusta* Linn. in streptozotocin induced diabetes. Indian Journal of clinical biochemistry. 2002; 17(2): pp. 33-43.
17. Ivy S, Hossain S, Labu ZK. Thrombolytic, antimicrobial and antioxidant activities of *Abroma augusta* L. leaves extract. 2019.
18. Kuadkaew S. Studies on analgesic, antipyretic and anti-inflammatory activities of *Abroma augusta* L. seed oil extract in experimental animals. 2010